

Title: Boosting the Silk tourism industry of Sualkuchi through the KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum project

Introduction: Sualkuchi is famous for golden silk Muga, and has the potential to boost tourism in Assam. However, the muga silk heritage is fast disappearing that now threatens the tourism industry of not only Sualkuchi but entire Assam.

Tourism is one of the fastest growing sectors in Indian economy. It is an industry which brings the world together, lead to exchange of knowledge, exchange of culture and foster international understanding. In rural India it provides the rural area people to explore their opportunity. It also provides economic growth of the people, provide development and also provide employment opportunity of the people of that area. Therefore, it is necessary to develop unique and innovative tourism project in Sualkuchi, one of the top attraction/destinations of many tourists visiting assam.

Our decades long research indicate that Sualkuchi was once a part of a historic silk road that stretch from North-Eastern Tibet to Myanmar, all the way to Cambodia. Ancient pilgrimage including Bon and Buddhist of Tibet used this road for trading to Kamrupa (the easternmost Mahajanapada of Vedic India), as well as Hindu states of south east Asia such as Champa (present day Vietnam and Cambodia). Ancient Kamrupa also used the silk road to trade with Tibet in north, and then South India, and South East Asia through the infamous Chittagong port in south (Recovering the spirit of Jiva Upakara Tantra (Vedic Altruism), chapter 5, ref).

Along this cross-road of two silk roads, cultural values, knowledges including medicinal knowledge grew for centuries. Our research on indigenous knowledge system further indicates that Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex was a key center of this silk road, where ancient Vedic Vartya culture prevailed, as indicated by ashram of numerous Vedic rishis such as Kanna Muni (Hajo), Vasishtha (Guwahati) and Kapil Muni (north Hajo). Moreover, during 6th-11th century era of Varman and Pal dynasty, there were frequent cultural exchange between Yunnan province of China in the East, and the Karnataka in the west along the Southern Silk Road corridor that went through the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex. Along these two silk routes, weavers of Sualkuchi area supplied the sacred muga cloth to numerous temples. Tibetan still believe that Bhagavan Buddha attained Nirvana in Hajo after wearing a sacred Mugabastra in Sualkuchi (Haajur Buronji, Dayal Krishna Bora, ref.). Thus, Vedic and Buddhist seers frequented along the silk road to visit the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex. However, the 12th-14th century of Islamic invasion destroyed the silk road culture/trade and knowledge growth

We are taking a unique, indigenous knowledge system based, “cultural emergence” approach (Globalization and emerging opportunities for Indigenous Cultures, Dr. Bikul Das, ref.) to revive and regenerate the VEDIC SILK ROAD HERITAGE OF SUALKUCHI/HAJO CULTURAL COMPLEX.

Photo 1: Ram-Rami Bastra

To revive the unique spiritual history of Sualkuchi silk industry, KaviKrishna produced many Ram-Ramibastra (**photo 1**) during 1975-80, and distributed among many Satras of Assam, and also several temples in Karnataka. A Vedic silk road-based tourism project plan was formulated and submitted to government through Lakshikanta Weaving Society in 1976, but the project plan did not materialize.

KaviKrishna has now revived this tourism project since 2010 as the Vedic Silk Road project, and has a grand plan to revive the entire road along the North Tibet to Myanmar/Thailand Hindu/Buddhist spiritual corridor. We have so far invested nearly 50 lakhs in historical/indigenous knowledge system/biochemical research to explore and establish the Vedic Silk Road among the international academic community in collaboration with the Thoreau lab for Global health, Massachusetts USA. Thus, we are committed to reviving the cultural and knowledge and medicinal heritage of the Sualkuchi/Hajo part of the Vedic silk route to attract national and international tourist. For this developmental plan, we have done both qualitative and quantitative research, and based on our findings, we have made a phase wise plan for the next 10 years. One of the plans is to set up the KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum in the historic Tantipara of Sualkuchi. This project is all about this Living Muga Museum project.

KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum: Preliminary work done:

To restore the muga heritage in Tantipara, we have been working since 2010 with two core families of Paresh Das, and Mano Das, and their supportive about 20 families. These families produced more than 150 mugathaans and sold in the market, and we kept 40 mugathaans for our research purpose. The Muga testing is then developing in lab-based method to test the purity of muga silk, as well to study the UV protective abilities of muga silk. Next, we have organized the KaviKrishna Telemedicine care to set up a muga production/museum unit and tied this project with our ongoing cancer patient rehabilitation project. In the KTC, since 2018, 130 cancer patients are registered, out of which 5 families are involved in the rehabilitation program. Our

aim is to engage total 100 cancer patient families in the next three years. We have used Muga silk weaving through IKS to rehabilitate the cancer patients. This rehabilitation project will help us to sustain the muga museum for long-term through national and international grant application for cancer rehabilitation. Next, we have set up so far one Muga loom in Biren Das house at Tantipara since 2020, and wanted to set up 5 more looms; covid19 pandemic slowed down the process. Our aim is to set up 20 muga looms in the Tantipara area so that the tourist can feel the heart-beat of weaving while visiting this historic Tantipara. Third, we have set up the herbal garden area, where we plan to grow trees to keep the live muga worm for tourist to see the process. Also, at the same time we want tourist to see all the herbal plants local to our area, and understand how we are doing herbal medicine research to enhance the muga worm yield and their health, thereby increasing the quality of muga thread. We have also planned Sualu plant in the herbal garden area; this tree is the unique for this area. Next, we have restored the Suad Muni Ashram, and KaviKrishna Sasang area for the tourist to sense the Vedic history of this area. Next, we are trying to revive the KaviKrishna Sasang (the area of Suad Muni Ashram) so that tourist can stay and feel the spiritual environment of the Sasang. In this manner, we aim to attract high end tourist, including university research team from all over the world to come, visit the Sualkchi-Hajo area and engage their research grant funds to enhance knowledge in multiple academic fields including Development Studies, Economies, cottage industry etc. In this context, we have yearly 200 dissertation targets, and already 10 students did dissertation, and two students are doing PhD research. We have now published a text book on muga to take forward this research tourist project. Importantly, we are also reviving the IKIN network through a Satra project having separate funding; the aim is to restore the spiritual connection of India's thousands of temples with muga silk. We aim to put at least one ram rami Muga bastra in each and every temple of India by 2030. People from these temples will then know about the unique Vedic silk heritage of Sualkuchi/Hajo cultural complex, and will come to visit our place. In this manner, our preliminary work is providing us with a strong basis to reach our vision to make the Vedic Silk Road project a grant success.

Project description: Our main goal is simple: we want tourist to walk down the Vedic Silk Road (shown in the map) to get a once in a life time experience of India's rich 5000 years old muga silk cultural heritage.

Photo 2: Map of Trekking Route

Revival of Vedic Silk Route by the living muga museum project:

Starting from Ishwar ShriShri Bordighi Satra to ancient Sasang KaviKrishna Xeel, then move on Vedic Saint Suadmuni cave (Near Brahmaputra River) and then Suadmuni cave to huge Suadmuni field, then through the KaviKrishna herbal garden we go to Tanti para; a historical place of Muga culture. Then Tanti para to ancient Hatisatra (Ancient Hindu Satra established in 17th century). Through the north gate of Hatisatra you can reach KTC (KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care) where visitors can know more about the project of cancer patient rehabilitation through KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum. Few steps from KTC visitors entered KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum (Research and Development site) where visitors can know more about the ongoing research and development project regarding Muga culture, Heritage, History etc. After that, visitors go to the ancient Siddheshwar Devalaya (An ancient temple of ancient Kamrupa link with Vedic Silk Route to Bhutan) then through the south gate of SiddheshwarDevalaya visitors can reach again Ishwar Shri ShriBordighiSatra the trekking ending point.

List of the places to be visited:

KaviKrishna Rock Xasang: The Kavikrishna Rock is a sacred ceremonial place known as Xasang, where siddhas did sacred bathing, and also chanting. For youth, it was a place for the right of passage including fasting, and a sacred bath. Bon pilgrimage of Tibet used to visit this rock for sacred ceremonies. In this sacred rock, Madhab Mahanta Bap used to sit and do contemplation for more than 30 years (1930-1963), when he lived in a small cottage at the Suadmuni ashram site, before become the Satradhikar of Hatisatra. A Bhutanese monk

Photo 3: KaviKrishna Xeel

visited the rock in 1940 to pray to Mahamuni (photo). The monk then visited the Bhimsankar Sasang at Rani of South Kamrup, Assam. The KaviKrishna and Bhimsankar rocks are ancient link of the Vedic silk road. Dr. Bikul Das met the Bhutanese monk in Mongar, Bhutan back in 1997, and learned about the ancient pilgrimage tie between Eastern Bhutan, and Sualkuchi's Siddheswar temple and KaviKrishna Xasang.

Our aim is to revive the same link to make awareness among the mass, especially among the young generations. It can be added here that the scientific voyage of Dr. Bikul Das had started from this KaviKrishna rock, the Sasang. Spectators bowed down to the KaviKrishna Rock hearing from us about the spiritual strength of the rock. In the flood season of spring and summer, we will

Photo 4: Dr. Bikul Das with the Bhutanese monk in Mongarh, Bhutan 1997

offer boat service for people to enjoy this area of the river and hill.

Suad Muni Ashram: As per the local legend, this cave and the surrounding area was the Ashram of a 10t century Siddha, Suad Muni. The Siddha started the KaviKrishna Xasang, and his philosophy was probably Vaishnav tantrism, and main mantra was Kavi-Krishna. The ashram was revived by Gandhian Jaykanta Das during 1910-30, where Hatisatra

Photo 5: Suad Muni Ashram

Satradhikar Madhav Mahanta lived for 30 years. The tantric Buddhist monks from Bhutan, and Tibet visited this sacred place annually at the time of visiting the Hayagriva Madhab. In the cave, they learned the “Nigudah” ritual of treating small pox. Jagat Ghora maintained the ancient Jiva Upakar Vada based tradition of an ancient ritual to treat patients suffering from small pox (Bikul Das, Facebook post, April 10, 2020). The stone hole on the floor of the cave was used for making herbal medicinal paste and also crude plasma therapy (buffalo blood) for treating sick people. The entire area of the cave, plus KaviKrishna rock and the hill plus the area was filled with Sualo tree for muga silk. The flow of Bhutiya pilgrims to this Suad Saint cave has been gradually diminishing since last two decades, resulting a loss of tourist department of the government of Assam. Photo is showing the students from management department of Asian Institute of Management and Technology exploring the cave of Suad Muni.

Tantipara Vedic Path: This Vedic Silk path is the remnant of an ancient road that connected the river with the Tantipara and connects some ancient historical importance places like KaviKrishna Stone, Saint Suad Muni Cave, Sualkuchi Tanti Para, Sipini Sangram Khetra, Ishwar SriSri HatiSatra. This road extends up to Bhimsagar Stone of the South of river Brahmaputra and to ancient Harrapan civilization at north. The Gandhian philosopher, Hembhai on 3rdFebruary 2020, re-opened that Silk Road.

Adarniya Binayak Kanetkor, the senior RSS Prasarak, who frequently visited to TantiPara during 1982 to 1985, Binayak ji used to encourage Mahindri Das, Sushila Das and her sisters as well as the weaver artist Krishna Ram Das at weaving skill.

Photo 6: Hem Bhai walking on the Tantipara Vedic Path

Photo 7: KaviKrishna team with Binayak Ji

KaviKrishna Herbal Garden: We have start up with the sapling of the herbal medicinal plant. The research students of KaviKrishna laboratory will have the research activity on Phytochemical and antioxidant activity of the medicinal plants of herbal garden in Guwahati Biotech Park. Our aim is to extend the herbal garden to Hajo area so to develop the IKIN

Photo 8: Students from AIMT in KaviKrishna Herbal Garden

network. Many local college students visited to this place for completion of their field study project work.

KaviKrishna Living MugaMuseum: Spectators are most welcome to KAVIKRISHNA LIVING MUGA MUSEUM to enjoy the entire process of preparing the Muga Bostra through various processes step by step. One can visualized the struggle of the weaver artist in muga culture revival. It includes –

- i. **Historic Tantipara:** Muga weaving was first introduced in Tantipara area of Sualkuchi. Tourist can able to interact with the Muga Artist about how they have been working on Muga Culture. Tourists can face the real weaver artists in Tantipara, having no perfectly pure product. Since the time of Mahapurush Srimanta Shankar Deva, weavers' generation after generation at Tantipara is working hard to revive the Muga culture.

- ii. **Sipini Sangram Khetra:** Name of the title reveals the significance of the site. Tourist can feel the struggle life of the weavers' artists by visiting the site. Besides they can predict the skill of the weavers' artist while they interact with the weavers at working period in Sipini Sangram khetra.

It is the place where the weaver artists struggle for the production of pure Muga cloth. It is also the place how the weaver artists struggle for collection of Muga cocoon, store them, cutting and weaving are done.

Photo 9: Students from AIMT at Sipini Sangram Khetra

iii. **Muga Artists of Tantipara:**

খাটি খোরা তাঁতী

কর্ম করে ওরে বাতি

শুদ্ধ পথত অটল

আজি যেন জীবন অচল।

Khati khowa Tati

Kormo kore ore rati

Sudha pothot atal

Agi jen jevan achal. (Pure is defeated by impure)

Photo 10: Muga Artist of Tantipara

Many artists in Tantipara living their lives through weaving. Here the tourist will see how Muga weaving are done and how the artists live their lives in reviving the muga culture.

iv. **Historic Tantipara Gate:** The Tantipara at Sualkuchi is where one can see the sub-branch of the Govardhan Math near the Jagannath Temple at Puri in Orissa. The soil from the Govardhan Math was brought and used at the time of construction of Kabindra Kutir. At the heart of the Kabindra Kutir, many philosophers like Hembhai, Dyal Krishna Bora and the poet Krishna Ram Das had discussions concerning the Hindutva ideology.

Photo 11: Cancer warriors and Muga Artists with the historic Tantipara Gate

Tourists who enter the Tantipara gate are attracted to the harmonious sounds of the fly shuttles of the handloom of the weavers who struggle to create the muga silk clothes from dawn to dusk. One can imagine the contribution of the skilled weaver artists to the

Photo 12: Map of Historic Tantipara

nation's economy. But sadly, no one seems to give them the recognition they deserve which is made worse by the decline in the weaving culture. Tourist can walk through the maze of small galis in the Tatipara to be part of the historic moment with weavers; they can spent the entire day roaming around in the red-ink area of Tatipara; we are planning to n=20 muga looms in this tatipara area so that tourists can feel at home, and be part of the life of a muga silk weaver, and at the same time enjoy the herbal gardening, as well as collecting their own herbs.

'KaviKrishna' which was earlier known as ' Krishna Samaj' has been endeavoring to revive and retain the original and rich environment of the Tantipara. Students are encouraged to do research on the biography of various weavers who were born in Tantipara since the establishment of Hatisatra.

Ishwar SriSri HatiSatra: Hatisatra is one of the biggest monasteries in the village Sualkuchi. Dedicated to Lord Krishna, the place spreads the splendid message of Vaishnavism culture. Established by Kanu Bura Thakur, a saint from Nalanga, this monastery today attracts pilgrim in large number and becoming a popular tourist attraction as well. Colorful Holi festival at Hatisatra attracts the pilgrims and during the time of Holi, many other festivals named 'Baah Bhonga' and "Krishna's Makhan Chor" is celebrated every year at Hatisatra moidan. Hatisatra was the pioneer religious institution where for the first time the birth anniversary of Mahapurush Srimanta Shankar Deva was celebrated.

Photo 14: Ishwar SriSri Hatisatra

Photo 13: During Holi at Hatisatra

KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care: Kavikrishna Telemedicine Care was from 1994 by Dr Bikul Das but officially it was from 2018. Till now 130 cancer patients of Hajo-Sualkuchi area has already registered. We provide recommendation, organized weekly counseling/focused group meetings with similar patients/families of the area.

Photo 15: Focus group discussion at KTC with Dr. Bikul Das

As most of the cancer patients are weaver so we have used Muga weaving through Indigenous knowledge system for cancer patient rehabilitation. Till now 5 cancer patient's families are engaged in this project.

Photo 16: Damayanti Devi: Breast cancer survivor and Bholaram Das: Cancer warrior

KaviKrishna Muga Museum Lab (Training and Research Site): Kavi Krishna Muga museum lab was set up for cancer patient rehabilitation. In addition, it helps the local artist and entrepreneurs.

We have developed a Muga course in a Muga Book, which will help the new generation to be aware about Muga culture of Sualkuchi. Teachers/professors of local schools/college will be able to deliver classes to interested students taking courses on Muga silk as a part of the social service curriculum or biotech curriculum of local colleges.

We have more than 20 volunteers including the students from local colleges who has been collecting different muga equipments and ancient designs developed by different muga weavers artist from Kamrup, Sualkuchi. We have preserved them in Muga Museum.

We would like to expands on our previous research work (Muga purity test by HPLC method) and Muga UV Ray protection study.

SriSri Siddheswar Devalaya: Siddheswar Devalaya is the most popular temple. Devotee Hindu's visit the temple very frequently in the honour of the great Lord Shiva, the Hindu deity and Shiba Singha. There are also lots of other individuals that visit the temple to pay their respect to Lord Shiva especially during Bole Bom, a festival that is celebrated with pomp. More over Shiva Ratri festival and a Joggya for the Shiva Ratri night is also held in every year in this Devalaya. In early days Buddhist from the Bhutan visited to this temple in Bhuddha Purnima.

Photo 17: Muga equipments collected by Muga Volunteers.

Photo 18: Muga Artists (Chitra Kalita, Lakhei das, Nalini Baishya and Mamoni Kalita) at KaviKrishna Muga Museum

Photo 19: HPLC graph of Muga purity testing

Photo 20: SriSri Siddheswar Devalaya

Photo 21: Yogya at SriSri Siddheswar Devalaya during Shiv Ratri Puja

Pond of Arimatta King: A historical pond situated in Rajgarh area of Sualkuchi nearby SriSri Siddheswar Devalaya. This pond was built by king Arimatta.

Photo 21: A Historical Pond build by King Arimatta

Eco-resort site: (Eco-tourism or ecological resort): we are trying to revive the KaviKrishna Sasang (the area of Suad Muni Ashram) so that tourist can stay and feel the spiritual environment of the Sasang.

Photo 24: Eco-resort Site

Notable Achievement so far: As the project KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum, Herbal Garden, Vedic silk route was started from 2019. It need time to set up. Collection of muga cocoons is very difficult as the production is low. Muga loom was provided to the people of Tantipara area. Collection of Silk worm, storing the Silk worm, silk reeling, dying and weaving process was distributed among the area. As the set up was in initial stage still the visitors from the colleges and tourist visited the place. Students from different colleges visited the places for their project work.

Spectators visiting Vedic silk route (Route from KaviKrishna Stone to SriSri Siddheswar Devalaya via KaviKrishna Muga Museum):

List of visitors have visited KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum and Trek:

1. **Hem Bhai:** On 3rd February 2020, prominent scholar Hem Bhai walks through the Vedic Silk Route as well as visited the Tantipara and KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum and praised the efforts of KaviKrishna for reviving this path and Tantipara and Muga Culture.
2. **IIT Student:** On February 2020, students from IIT Guwahati visited KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum.
3. Students from different schools of Sualkuchi are visited KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum.
4. **S.B.M.S. College student visit:** A group of more than 100 students from S.B.M.S College visited KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum on March 2021 as a part of their project field visit.
5. **Cotton College student visit:** On September 2021 a group of students from Cotton College visited KaviKarishna Living Muga Museum.
6. **Bamundi College Student visit:** On September 2021, a group of students from Bamundi College visited KaviKrishna living Muga Museum and also did dissertation with us.
7. **AIMT Student visit:** A group of 40 students from Asian Institute of Management and Technology visited KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum as a part academical field visit.
8. **NavadeepKalitavisits:** Vice-chairman of Tourism, Assam Govt. Shri NavadeepKalita visited KaviKrishna living Muga Museum and Trek.
9. **Seri-culture dept. visit:** A team of Seri-culture dept. govt. of Assam under the guidance of Assistant Director of Seri-culture dept. Mr. Utpal Chakraborty visited KaviKrishna living Muga Museum.
10. **Visitors from Maharastra:** A group of people from Maharastra visited KaviKrishna living Muga Museum.

Student Dissertation:

KaviKrishna living Muga Museum ask for the students from different schools and colleges and provide required raw materials, experts, field to do dissertation on Muga Culture. This academic project is already started and till now we have received 10 dissertations from the students from different college. KaviKrishna living Muga Museum planning to have 200 dissertations from the students from different schools and colleges and also workshop on Muga culture, Heritage etc.

Ongoing project-

- **Cancer rehabilitation program:** KaviKrishna telemedicine care has already registered 130 cancer patients till now. As most of the cancer patients are weaver so we have used Muga weaving for cancer patient rehabilitation.
- **Muga museum:** We have developed a muga course in the muga museum where teachers/professors of local schools/college will be able to deliver classes to interested students taking courses on muga silk as a part of the social service curriculum or biotech curriculum of local colleges.
- **Muga book** is prepared–
 - New generation will be aware about the Muga culture of Sualkuchi.
 - Will extend the research field of the ancient Muga culture related activities.
 - Will make a strong network of Hajo-Sualkuchi people.
 - migrant students will spread the Muga culture to rest of the country.
 - If someone intended to start a handloom industry, she/ he can proceed on following the Muga book.
- **Dissertation:** We have planned to collect 200 dissertations from the students in a year. We have already collected 15 dissertations from the students. So that we can develop the students in the research area. And also help to develop network system.
- **Herbal garden:** We have start up with the sapling of the herbal medicinal plant. Phytochemical and antioxidant activity of the medicinal plant will be checked in Guwahati Biotech Park by the research students. The herbal garden will be extended to Hajo area so to develop the IKIN network
- **KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum:** Muga loom and muga cocoons cutting and reeling process is set up in KaviKrishna living museum among the 1muga artist at tantipara. One of our registered cancer patient Damayanti Devi with his husband Siddhi Sarma working as a Muga weaving part in KaviKrishna Muga Museum.

- **Muga purity testing:** Muga than produced in the KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum are tested for purity in KaviKrishna Laboratory, IIT Guwahati through HPLC.
- **Muga Book:** A Muga Book, named (Jiva Upakar Baador Joriyote Muga Silpor Punoruddhar) prepared which will help the new generation to be aware about Muga culture of Sualkuchi. It also helps to extend the research field of ancient Muga culture related activities. It will make a strong network of Hajo-Sualkuchi people among the culture.
- **Muga loom:** One Muga loom is set up at the KaviKrishna muga museum for training and research and one muga loom is set up at KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum at Tantipara Muga artist (Biren da house) for the revival of muga culture.

Employment possibility: As KaviKrishna has 40 Muga than prepared by 16 cancer patients' families till 2019. We have estimated to produce 200 muga than which will prove employments to the 100 cancer patient's families.

Engagement in weaving artist: This project will contribute to income opportunities. Tourism will create jobs in local tourism sectors as well as local sector. It will help the income opportunities of the 100 local weaver artist families by weaving muga cloth. It will also help in reviving muga culture heritage.

Volunteer's involvement: We have more than 20 volunteers including the students from local colleges who has been collecting different muga equipments and ancient designs developed by different muga weavers artist from Kamrup, Sualkuchi. We have preserved them in Muga Museum.

Engagement of local artist in designing It will also contribute to facilitating its domestic sector. Local artist in designing and selling of the muga cloth can be help in engaged in muga culture reviving. It will also attract investment in the region. It will promote local economic system with income opportunities throughout the year.

Cultural heritage: It will also help in reviving the Vedic silk heritage of the sualkuchi-hajo area. It will also help in economic and social development of the region.

Scope-

- Provide economically development of the weaver artist of that area
- Revive the cultural heritage of the area
- Marketing will be more
- Export opportunities
- Provide employment.

Tentative Budget:

Income Section	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Total
Individual Contribution				
Community Charities				
Government Funding	25,59,600.00	18,54,300.00	15,89,400.00	60,03,300.00
United Way Finding				
Sponsorship				
Foundations/Corporation Funding	2,84,400.00			2,84,400.00
Alternative ways of generating revenue		7,94,700.00	10,59,600.00	18,54,300.00
Income Total	28,44,000.00	26,49,000.00	26,49,000.00	81,42,000.00
Tentative Expense Section	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Total
Manpower	17,52,000.00	17,52,000.00	17,52,000.00	52,56,000.00
Herbal garden setup and maintenance cost	1,50,000.00	1,00,000.00	1,00,000.00	3,50,000.00
Travel & Lodging	50,000.00	50,000.00	50,000.00	1,50,000.00
Temporary Labor	52,000.00	52,000.00	52,000.00	1,56,000.00
Printing/Publication Cost	80,000.00	80,000.00	80,000.00	2,40,000.00
Project Management Fees	2,00,000.00	2,00,000.00	2,00,000.00	6,00,000.00
Computer and other accessories	1,00,000.00	20,000.00	20,000.00	1,40,000.00
Web Development & Hosting	1,00,000.00	35,000.00	35,000.00	1,70,000.00
Training Cost	80,000.00	80,000.00	80,000.00	2,40,000.00
Museum Rent	1,20,000.00	1,20,000.00	1,20,000.00	3,60,000.00
Electricity and other cost	60,000.00	60,000.00	60,000.00	1,80,000.00
Miscellaneous	1,00,000.00	1,00,000.00	1,00,000.00	3,00,000.00
Total (Year wise)	28,44,000.00	26,49,000.00	26,49,000.00	
Grand Total				81,42,000.00

Justification

- A. **Government Funding:** 90%, 70% and 60% respectively for the FY-1, FY-2 and FY-3.
- B. **Foundations/Corporation Funding:** Kavikrishna foundation already invested 50 lakhs for the set up of the Muga Living Museum and Muga Museum Lab since 2010. Kavikrishna foundation also ready to distribute 20 muga than (approx. Rs 10 lakhs value) at different religious temple complex to re unite the historic vedic silk route.
- C. **Alternative ways of generating revenue:** 30% and 40% revenue will be collected for FY-2 and FY-3

C.1. Revenue will be collected from

- From Tourist visitors
- Selling of muga than
- Through FCRA/Thoreau Lab, MA, USA

D. Details of Manpower:

Sl. No.	Job description	No of Post	Monthly stipend	Annual stipend
1	Tourist Guide	1	30000×1=30,000.00	3,60,000.00
2	Office Assistant	1	20000×1=20,000.00	2,40,000.00
3	Care taker	2	10000×2=20,000.00	2,40,000.00
4	Gardener	2	18000×2=36,000.00	4,32,000.00
5	Weaver Artist	4	10000×4=40,000.00	4,80,000.00
Total Stipend				17,52,000.00

Kavi Krishna Laboratory
Guwahati Biotech Park, IIT-Guwahati
Email Id: kavikrishnalab@gmail.com
Phone No: 8135857637, 8471838003.

To

Dr. Ravi Kota, I.A.S
Commissioner & Secretary
Department of Finance, Government of Assam,
Assam Sachivalaya, Dispur, Guwahati 781 006

Sub: Cover Letter for Muga Project Proposal Entitled- *“Development of A Novel Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS) Analysis method for Identification of Source of the Pure Muga Thread in Assam”*

Dear Raviji,

It was a privilege interacting with you on 7th May 2016 regarding the Muga Project. Your vast knowledge on Muga and your plans for its up-gradation of the business and Assam's traditional culture has immensely inspired me. You have really encouraged me to continue my work on finding the pure Muga thread source along with my team.

On the above proposal I even had a meeting with the Honorable Chief-Secretary of Assam on 5th May 2016 and Mr Vinod Seshan (CEO of GBP, IIT-G) on 6th May 2016. They had shown great interest in this topic and had asked my team to submit the proposal along with budget to the finance department with an assurance of positivity towards the project.

Initially, we had submitted project to various departments of Assam government from where the submissions were accepted or scored well, but then the funding has not reached to us yet. So, we are losing our hopes on the governing heads but still want to continue our work for the futility of the indigenous masses who are the sufferers.

These meetings has fruited a ray of hope again where your initiative for helping the Muga industry is also our motto too. We are greatly looking forward for working together with your support so that the benefit can reach the suffering masses waiting for some miracle to let their traditional heritage survive.

Thank you for taking the time to read this letter, and I look forward to your response, not just to acknowledge the letter, but a response and supports that gives us all hope.

Yours sincerely,

Bikul Das, MBBS, PhD (Director)
Kavi Krishna Laboratory
Guwahati Biotech Park
IIT-Guwahati

Copy to: Mr Vinod Shesan (CEO, Guwahati Biotech Park, IIT-Guwahati)
Kavi Krishna Laboratory (Guwahati Biotech Park, IIT-Guwahati)

Please find the following attachment: 1) Proposal Copy along with detailed Budget

PROJECT ON

Development of A Novel Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS) Analysis method for Identification of Source of the Pure Muga Thread in Assam

Submitted By

Kavi-Krishna Laboratory (KKL)

Guwahati Biotech Park (GBP), Indian Institute of Technology- Guwahati (IIT-G)

Submitted To

Government of Assam

Dated: 04/06/2016

Development of A Novel Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS) Analysis method for Identification of Source of the Pure Muga Thread in Assam

Kavi-Krishna Laboratory, GBP, IIT-G

Summary:

Kavi Krishna has been dedicated since its foundation in 1920 in helping the silk weavers who have survived through the generations for production of pure Muga. Muga industry has been the traditional identity of Assam which is slowly dying because of the constant degradation of pure Muga source or entry of impure Muga silk. Kavi Krishna Laboratory has come up with a solution to this problem by identifying the pure Muga silk from impure one using standard GC-MS analysis method. Till date, KKL has utilized a capital sum of approximately 20 lakhs for making this project run successfully by helping the silk weavers for weaving pure Muga thaans and even constructing the Muga Museum and Emporium at Hatigaon for later mass production of pure Muga.

Rationale:

Muga industry has been traditionally a mark of cultural identity of Assam but recent entry of impure or false Muga silk like Tassar has dramatically threatened the traditional Muga industry. Importantly, the source of pure Muga thread is declining. One of the potential solutions to this problem is the establishment of testing laboratory that can distinguish pure Muga silk from impure one. Currently, several methods have been used to test the purity of Muga threads. These methods are based on the physical cross-sectioning of the Muga silk under microscope or chemical testing that can separate Muga from other threads including Tassar and Eri. However, these methods are not being able to identify the best Muga threads. We henceforth, reason that developing a sophisticated pure Muga thread Assay could help us to identify the source of best Muga thread. Here, we hypothesize that Gas-Chromatography Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS) analysis could be used to develop a Pure Muga Test Assay (PMTA). GC-MS have been successfully used to identify distinct spectrum of complex organic compounds including fabrics. Hence, we hypothesize that this sophisticated analysis could be utilized to identify the purity of Muga thread with high quality fabric. We speculated that GC-MS method could be utilized to test the commercial available Muga thread and in this manner thus identify the best source of Muga thread in Lower Assam.

The source of Muga thread in Assam is heterogeneous. Different farmers have different trends for cultivating Muga. The collection of cocoons utilized for weaning of Muga threads are gathered from different sources. Even the weaver community can distinguish different types of Muga thread depending upon seasonal variation. These vague identifications or experiments cannot determine the specific source of Muga thread having the good quality out product.

We suggest that GC-MS analysis will certify the specific source of best quality Muga thread by random analysis of only commercially available Muga Fabric in the market.

Taken together we are attempting to develop a Sophisticated Analytical Muga Thread Testing Assay that will not only signify the purity of Muga thread but also identify the specific source of the best Muga thread in Assam.

Innovation:

The research to identify the source and best Muga thread is not helping us. Our project is innovative because we for the very fast time are developing a Muga testing assay based on Sophisticated Analytics that is specifically focused on commercially available Muga thread so that it can be valuable for the genuine suppliers and the buyers.

Experimental plan:

AIM 1: Define the GC-MS of the Muga thread: For this purpose, we have already produced 40 than of pure muga {cocoons being collected from Som plants were weaved by Muga experts (Mr. Manoranjan Das & Mr. Parash.Ch. Baishya) of Kavi-Krishna NGO, Sualkuchi} and being tested at the Sualkuchi Muga Testing Laboratory (SMTL). The 40 than muga threads will be subjected to confocal microscopic analysis followed by GC-MS resolution. Additionally, we plan to test the quality of Muga thread obtained from muga cocoon raised in Soalu plant, a historical plant being mentioned in Sualkuchi history, and that the name of Sualkuchi is derived from this Soalu plant. For this purpose, we have found wild Soalu plant in geographically conserved area (Rakhashini Pahar and Phulbari Pahar in greater Sualkuchi area) whose cocoons can be used as a standard of pure Muga for this analysis.

AIM 2: Compare the quality of seasonal muga thread by GC-MS. We found that there is traditional knowledge about differing quality of seasonal muga. However, so far no testing method has been developed to confirm the quality of seasonal muga. We hypothesize that GC MS will enable us to confirm the traditional knowledge about seasonal muga (e.g. whether muga produced in April-June month is good or bad as compared to October-December month?). Since the weavers say that quality of Muga differs accordingly to season, it is important to confirm their assumption with a concrete scientific method. Thus, our GC MS method will be of tremendous help for the muga weavers to find out the best quality of season muga, and accordingly obtain high price for their best quality muga .For this aim, we will collect the season muga thread and confirm the purity using GC-MS.

AIM 3: Define the best source of the Muga thread: In this aim we shall obtain samples based on power analysis of the Muga thread based on Aim 1 and Aim 2 collected randomly from Sualkuchi Muga stores. These Muga threads would be subjected to GC-MS spectra. Identification of the source of the best Muga thread will help us to trace the farmers who are producing those specific Muga larvae or the Muga cocoon.

AIM 4: Establishment of Kavi-Krishna Muga Museum & Emporium: Kavi Krishna has been dedicated since its foundation in 1920 in helping the silk weavers who have survived through the generations for production of pure Muga. Specifically, we have been working since 2012 for the current project, and so far produced and stored 40 pure muga than, and also constructing a muga museum in Hatigaon land being leased from Mrs Mahindri Das, the patron of Kavi Krishna. Then, specifically for the current project, we are producing muga than since 2012 with the help of Monoranjan Das and Paresh Baishya, and produced 40 pure muga than for our research. Thus, we have tremendous history on muga/silk area, and specifically working for the project since 2012. We have also started constructing the muga museum/emporium in Hatigaon since 2013.

Preliminary Data:

Kavi Krishna Muga had initiated this project in 2012 and so far collected 40 pure Muga thaans (12 meter long pure Muga fabric) samples. These Muga thaans are undergoing purity testing in the Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory. These best pure thaans will be selected for the Aim-1 study. For the microscopic Muga testing of the thaans we will perform additional confocal microscopic testing

and evaluate the images to find the best quality Muga than. Further, the best selected than shall be subjected to GC-MS studies.

Time Line:

AIM 1: 6 months-40 samples, Total Budget- 17 lakhs (Approx).

AIM 2: 6 months-30 samples, Total Budget-14 lakhs (Approx).

AIM 3: 6 months-10 samples preliminary followed by power analysis to obtain the minimum number of samples to testify the market, Total Budge-15lakhs (Approx).

AIM 4: Establishment of Kavi- Krishna Muga Museum and Emporium for benefit to the indigenous mass dedicated to pure Muga production-50lakhs (Approx).

Feasibility:

It is possible to complete this study in our laboratory because Kavi-Krishna Muga Laboratory is a part of Kavi-Krishna having own production unit for producing pure Muga Thaan. Kavi-Krishna Laboratory has access to GC-MS present at GBP. We have trained scientist having experience in imaging extraction, GC-MS analysis. In addition, Kavi-Krishna Laboratory has access to the Harvard University Catalyst Laboratory having renowned GC-MS facility.

Expectations:

We expect to find distinct GC-MS spectra for pure Muga thread. We expect that Aim-2 and Aim-3 will allow us to source the best Muga thread to be circulated from Assam. Importantly, we expect that our collaboration with Sualkuchi Muga Testing Laboratory will initiate a new direction for Kavi-Krishna Laboratory to contribute to social and community cost of the Muga heritage.

Future Direction:

In future, the GC-MS spectra for Muga will help us study the health benefit effects of pure Muga thread. Further, finding the pure source shall help the buyers to trace the original suppliers of Muga who are indigenously involved through generations in yielding the Muga heritage that is now losing its ground. Prevailing so, in future a geologically conserved suitable area can be allotted for culture of pure Muga thus following its supply in the market in long term prospected project.

Figure 01: Preliminary Work done till date for Analysis of Muga purity

Budget Particulars for Kavi-Krishna Laboratory (KKL), Guwahati
Biotech Park (GBP), IIT-Guwahati

(I) RECURRING BUDGET (IN RUPEES) FOR AIM 1: (Timeline: 6 Months)

A. HUMAN RESOURCES TO BE INVOLVED

<u>Human Resource to be involved with the project</u>									
Sl. No.	Position	No of Positions	Qualification	Age (In years)	Experience (In Years)	Duration for which to be Hired (In Months)	Role in the Project	Proposed Monthly Salary (Rs.In Lakhs) (for e.g. 50,000 can be written as 0.50)	Total cost (Rs.In lakhs)
1.	Consultant Scientist	1	Ph. D Holder	Not more than 40	3-5 years of experience in the relevant field	6	He/She should take care of all data analysis and direction of the project work line.	@ 0.10	0.60
2.	Junior Research Scientist	2	M. Sc Biotech-nology	Not more than 35	3-5 years of experience in the relevant field.	6	They should take care of all experimental plans and procedure include in Muga research.	@ 0.30 x 2 = 0.60 + 10% HRA	3.96
3.	Junior Research Assistant	1	M. Sc Biotech-nology	Not more than 30	1-2 years of experience in the relevant field.	6	He/She should take care of all experimental part include in Muga research.	@ 0.15 + 10% HRA	0.99
4.	Field Assistant	1	12 th Standard (Preferably have knowledge on Muga silk)	Not more than 25	1-2 years of experience in the relevant field	6	The field assistant will take care of collection and microscopy testing of Muga Silk from market.	0.7 + 10% HRA	0.46
Total Cost : 6.01 lakhs									

B. COST OF CONSUMABLES

Through GBP contribution					
Sl. No.	Items	Justification for the Requirement	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Approximate Cost (Rs. In Lakhs) for 24 months project (Approx.)
1.	Space for Laboratory	For doing Muga Research work	-	854 Square feet (per Square feet= Rs. 40) 34,160/month	2.05
2.	Internet Charges	For searching Research Papers	1	1000/month	0.06
3.	Electricity Charges for Lab	For constant supply of electricity.	-	10,000/month	0.60
4.	Laminar Air Flow	For Sample preparation	-	365/day for 1 months	0.11
5.	Confocal Microscope	For Analysis of Samples	40 samples (for 10 hrs)	3000/two hours	0.15
6.	Balance	For Sample balancing	40 samples (for 10 hrs)	20/per hour	-
7.	Ultra-Sonicator	For Sample preparation	20 Samples	100/per sample	0.02
8	Rotary Evaporator (5 L)	For drying of Sample	20 Samples	500/per litre	0.10
9.	GC-MS	For Analysis of Sample	4 Samples * 3 times = 12 samples	800/per sample	0.10
					Total: 3.19 lakhs

c. OTHER RECURRING HEADS

Sl.No	Other Cost (Rs.in lakhs)	Justification																														
1.	6.48	<p>Under this head { main tenancy of purchase of MugaThaans from renowned suppliers of Sualkuchi through Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory certified under Silk Mark Khanapara, Guwahati } to be used on payment basis for the proposed experiment as outlined below:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Sl.No.</th> <th>Specific Requirement In The Project</th> <th>Quantity</th> <th>Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)</th> <th>Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1.</td> <td>Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)</td> <td>40</td> <td>15,000/Mugathaans</td> <td>6.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.</td> <td>Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory</td> <td>40</td> <td>100/sample</td> <td>0.04</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.</td> <td>Solvents for analysis</td> <td>8 litres</td> <td>500/litre</td> <td>0.04</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4.</td> <td>Desktop & Color printer for Muga Laboratory</td> <td>1+1</td> <td>40,000/desktop</td> <td>0.40</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5" style="text-align: right;">Total:6.48 lakhs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Sl.No.	Specific Requirement In The Project	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)	1.	Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)	40	15,000/Mugathaans	6.00	2.	Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory	40	100/sample	0.04	3.	Solvents for analysis	8 litres	500/litre	0.04	4.	Desktop & Color printer for Muga Laboratory	1+1	40,000/desktop	0.40	Total:6.48 lakhs				
Sl.No.	Specific Requirement In The Project	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)																												
1.	Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)	40	15,000/Mugathaans	6.00																												
2.	Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory	40	100/sample	0.04																												
3.	Solvents for analysis	8 litres	500/litre	0.04																												
4.	Desktop & Color printer for Muga Laboratory	1+1	40,000/desktop	0.40																												
Total:6.48 lakhs																																
2.	0.25 (Contingency)	This budget will cover the cost of patenting the research discovery, routine lab requirements including cotton roll, tissue roll, aluminum foil, printing –cartridges, desktop requirements, publication and presentation, and other unforeseen essential cost .																														
3.	0.25 (Travel Grant)	The budget will meet the expenses of field visit for sample collection, visit to the collaborating institute (Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory), participation in the review meeting and seminar/symposium/conference related to the project.																														
		Total: 6.98 lakhs																														

BUDGET DETAILSFor AIM 1

<u>Recurring Cost (Rs.In Lakhs)</u>			
Human Resources(A)	Consumables(B)	Other Heads(C)	Total (A+B+C)
6.01	3.19	6.98	16.18

(II) RECURRING BUDGET (IN RUPEES) FOR AIM 2: (Timeline: 6 Months)

A. HUMAN RESOURCES TO BE INVOLVED

<u>Human Resource to be involved with the project</u>									
Sl. No.	Position	No of Positions	Qualification	Age (In years)	Experience (In Years)	Duration for which to be Hired (In Months)	Role in the Project	Proposed Monthly Salary (Rs.In Lakhs) (for e.g. 50,000 can be written as 0.50)	Total cost (Rs.In lakhs)
1.	Consultant Scientist	1	Ph. D Holder	Not more than 40	3-5 years of experience in the relevant field	6	He/She should take care of all data analysis and direction of the project work line.	@ 0.15	0.90
2.	Junior Research Scientist	2	M. Sc Biotechnology	Not more than 35	3-5 years of experience in the relevant field.	6	They should take care of all experimental plans and procedure include in Muga research.	(@ 0.35+ 10% HRA) x 2	4.62
3.	Junior Research Assistant	1	M. Sc Biotechnology	Not more than 30	1-2 years of experience in the relevant field.	6	He/She should take care of all experimental part include in Muga research.	@ 0.20 + 10% HRA	1.32
4.	Field Assistant	1	12 th Standard (Preferably have knowledge on Muga silk)	Not more than 25	1-2 years of experience in the relevant field	6	The field assistant will take care of collection and microscopy testing of Muga Silk from market.	@ 0.7 + 10% HRA	0.46
Total Cost :7.3 lakhs									

B. COST OF CONSUMABLES

<u>Through GBP contribution</u>					
Sl. No.	Items	Justification for the Requirement	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Approximate Cost (Rs. In Lakhs) for 24 months project (Approx.)
1.	Space for Laboratory	For doing Muga Research work	-	854 Square feet (per Square feet= Rs. 40)34,160/month	2.05
2.	Internet Charges	For searching Research Papers	1	1000/month	0.06
3.	Electricity Charges for Lab	For constant supply of electricity.	-	10,000/month	0.60
4.	Laminar Air Flow	For Sample preparation	-	365/day for 1 months	0.11
5.	Confocal Microscope	For Analysis of Samples depending seasonal collection (6 seasons)	6*3=18 samples (for 8hrs)	3000/two hours	0.10
6.	Balance	For Sample balancing	18 samples (for 10 hrs)	20/per hour	-
7.	Ultra-Sonicator	For Sample preparation	18 Samples	100/per sample	0.02
8	Rotary Evaporator (5 L)	For drying of Sample	18 Samples	500/per litre	0.08
9.	GC-MS	For Analysis of Sample	6 Samples * 3 times = 18 samples	800/per sample	0.15
Total: 3.17 lakhs					

c. OTHER RECURRING HEADS

Sl.No	Other Cost (Rs.in lakhs)	Justification																									
1.	2.76	Under this head {main tenancy of purchase of MugaThaans from renowned suppliers of Sualkuchi through Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory certified under Silk Mark Khanapara, Guwahati} to be used on payment basis for the proposed experiment as outlined below: <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Sl.No.</th> <th>Specific Requirement In The Project</th> <th>Quantity</th> <th>Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)</th> <th>Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1.</td> <td>Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)</td> <td>18</td> <td>15,000/Mugathaans</td> <td>2.70</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.</td> <td>Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory</td> <td>18</td> <td>100/sample</td> <td>0.02</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.</td> <td>Solvents for analysis</td> <td>8 litres</td> <td>500/litre</td> <td>0.04</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5" style="text-align: right;">Total: 2.76 lakhs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Sl.No.	Specific Requirement In The Project	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)	1.	Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)	18	15,000/Mugathaans	2.70	2.	Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory	18	100/sample	0.02	3.	Solvents for analysis	8 litres	500/litre	0.04	Total: 2.76 lakhs				
Sl.No.	Specific Requirement In The Project	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)																							
1.	Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)	18	15,000/Mugathaans	2.70																							
2.	Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory	18	100/sample	0.02																							
3.	Solvents for analysis	8 litres	500/litre	0.04																							
Total: 2.76 lakhs																											
2.	0.25 (Contingency)	This budget will cover the cost of patenting the research discovery, routine lab requirements including cotton roll, tissue roll, aluminum foil, printing –cartridges, desktop requirements, publication and presentation, and other unforeseen essential cost .																									
3.	0.25 (Travel Grant)	The budget will meet the expenses of field visit for sample collection, visit to the collaborating institute (Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory), participation in the review meeting and seminar/symposium/conference related to the project.																									
		Total: 3.26 lakhs																									

BUDGET DETAILS For AIM 2

<u>Recurring Cost (Rs.In Lakhs)</u>			
Human Resources(A)	Consumables(B)	Other Heads(C)	Total (A+B+C)
7.3	3.17	3.26	13.73

(III) RECURRING BUDGET (IN RUPEES) FOR AIM 3: (Timeline: 6 Months)

A. HUMAN RESOURCES TO BE INVOLVED

<u>Human Resource to be involved with the project</u>									
Sl. No.	Position	No of Positions	Qualification	Age (In years)	Experi-ence (In Years)	Dura-tion for which to be Hired (In Months)	Role in the Project	Proposed Monthly Salary (Rs.In Lakhs) (for e.g. 50,000 can be written as 0.50)	Total cost (Rs.In lakhs)
1.	Consultant Scientist	1	Ph. D Holder	Not more than 40	4-6 years of experience in the relevant field	6	He/She should take care of all data analysis and direction of the project work line.	@ 0.20	1.20
2.	Junior Research Scientist	2	Ph. D Holder	Not more than 35	1-2 years of experience in the relevant field	6	They should take care of all experimental plans and procedure include in Muga research.	(@ 0.40+ 10% HRA) x 2	5.28
3.	Junior Research Assistant	1	M. Sc Biotechnology	Not more than 30	2-3 years of experience in the relevant field	6	He/She should take care of all experimental part include in Muga research.	@ 0.25 + 10% HRA	1.65
4.	Field Assistant	1	12 th Standard (Preferably have knowledge on Muga silk)	Not more than 25	1-2 years of experience in the relevant field	6	The field assistant will take care of collection and microscopy testing of Muga Silk from market.	0.10 + 10% HRA	0.66
Total Cost : 8.79 lakhs									

B. COST OF CONSUMABLES

<u>Through GBP contribution</u>					
Sl. No.	Items	Justification for the Requirement	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Approximate Cost (Rs. In Lakhs) for 24 months project (Approx.)
1.	Space for Laboratory	For doing Muga Research work	-	854 Square feet (per Square feet= Rs. 40)34,160/month	2.05
2.	Internet Charges	For searching Research Papers	1	1000/month	0.06
3.	Electricity Charges for Lab	For constant supply of electricity.	-	10,000/month	0.60
4.	Laminar Air Flow	For Sample preparation	-	365/day for 1 months	0.11
5.	Confocal Microscope	For Analysis of Samples depending seasonal collection (6 seasons)	10 samples (for 6hrs)	3000/two hours	0.09
6.	Balance	For Sample balancing	10 samples (for 3hrs)	20/per hour	-
7.	Ultra-Sonicator	For Sample preparation	10 Samples	100/per sample	0.01
8	Rotary Evaporator (5 L)	For drying of Sample	10 Samples	500/per litre	0.05
9.	GC-MS	For Analysis of Sample	10 samples	800/per sample	0.08
Total: 3.86 lakhs					

c. OTHER RECURRING HEADS

Sl.No	Other Cost (Rs.in lakhs)	Justification																									
1.	1.53	Under this head { main tenancy of purchase of MugaThaans from renowned suppliers of Sualkuchi through Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory certified under Silk Mark Khanapara, Guwahati } to be used on payment basis for the proposed experiment as outlined below: <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Sl.No.</th> <th>Specific Requirement In The Project</th> <th>Quantity</th> <th>Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)</th> <th>Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1.</td> <td>Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)</td> <td>10</td> <td>15,000/Mugathaans</td> <td>1.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.</td> <td>Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory</td> <td>10</td> <td>100/sample</td> <td>0.01</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.</td> <td>Solvents for analysis</td> <td>4 litres</td> <td>500/litre</td> <td>0.02</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5" style="text-align: right;">Total: 1.53 lakhs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Sl.No.	Specific Requirement In The Project	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)	1.	Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)	10	15,000/Mugathaans	1.5	2.	Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory	10	100/sample	0.01	3.	Solvents for analysis	4 litres	500/litre	0.02	Total: 1.53 lakhs				
Sl.No.	Specific Requirement In The Project	Quantity	Units (e.g:-g/ml etc)	Estimated Value(Rs.In Lakhs)																							
1.	Sample For analysis (MugaThaans)	10	15,000/Mugathaans	1.5																							
2.	Preliminary Analysis from Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory	10	100/sample	0.01																							
3.	Solvents for analysis	4 litres	500/litre	0.02																							
Total: 1.53 lakhs																											
2.	0.25 (Contingency)	This budget will cover the cost of patenting the research discovery, routine lab requirements including cotton roll, tissue roll, aluminum foil, printing –cartridges, desktop requirements, publication and presentation, and other unforeseen essential cost .																									
3.	0.25 (Travel Grant)	The budget will meet the expenses of field visit for sample collection, visit to the collaborating institute (Sualkuchi Silk Testing Laboratory), participation in the review meeting and seminar/symposium/conference related to the project.																									
		Total: 2.03 lakhs																									

BUDGET DETAILS For AIM 3

<u>Recurring Cost (Rs.In Lakhs)</u>			
Human Resources(A)	Consumables(B)	Other Heads(C)	Total (A+B+C)
8.79	3.86	2.03	14.68

Grand Total of Muga Project Uptill AIM 3

{AIM 1(Rs.16.18 lakhs) + AIM 2 (Rs.13.73 lakhs) + AIM 3 (Rs.14.68 lakhs)} + Overhead Charges @ 10%

=

Rs. (44.59 lakhs +4.46 lakhs) = Rs. 49.05 lakhs

BUDGET DETAILS For AIM 1 (Page No.- 5-7)

<u>Recurring Cost (Rs.In Lakhs)</u>			
Human Resources(A)	Consumables(B)	Other Heads(C)	Total (A+B+C)
6.01	3.19	6.98	16.18

BUDGET DETAILS For AIM 2 (Page No. 8-10)

<u>Recurring Cost (Rs.In Lakhs)</u>			
Human Resources(A)	Consumables(B)	Other Heads(C)	Total (A+B+C)
7.3	3.17	3.26	13.73

BUDGET DETAILS For AIM 3 (Page No.11-13)

<u>Recurring Cost (Rs.In Lakhs)</u>			
Human Resources(A)	Consumables(B)	Other Heads(C)	Total (A+B+C)
8.79	3.86	2.03	14.68

AIM 4

Establishment of Kavi- Krishna Muga Museum and Emporium at Hatigaon, Guwahatifer benefit to the indigenous mass dedicated to pure Muga production-50 lakhs (Approx).

Kavi Krishna has been dedicated since its foundation in 1920 in helping the silk weavers who have survived through the generations for production of pure Muga. Specifically, we have been working since 2012 for the current project, and so far produced and stored 40 pure muga than, and also constructed a muga museum in Hatigaon land being leased from Mrs Mahindri Das, the patron of Kavi Krishna. Then, specifically for the current project, we are producing muga than since 2012 with the help of Monoranjan Das and Paresh Baishya, and produced 40 pure muga than for our research. Thus, we have tremendous history on muga/silk area, and specifically working for the project since 2012. We have also started constructing the muga museum/emporium in Hatigaon since 2013

RECURRING COST FOR ESTABLISHMENTOF KAVI KRISHNA MUGA MUSEUM & EMPORIUM

<u>Sl. No.</u>	<u>Items</u>	<u>Quantity</u>	<u>Approximate Cost (Rs. In Lakhs) for 24 months project (Approx.)</u>	<u>Remarks</u>
1.	Free Space taken for lease of 10 years	1 katta space	5	Already Paid By Kavi Krishna NGO
2	Started making Rooms for the Muga museum from Jan 2015-april 2016	1 office Room, 2 Small Room , 1 Big room & 1 bathroom	10	Already Paid By Kavi Krishna NGO
3	Muga Museum & Emporium	1 office Room, 2 Small Room , 1 Big room & 1 bathroom (Details in Sketch Below)	35	-
Total : 50 Lakhs				

Sketch of Kavi-Krishna Muga Museum and Emporium at Puberun Path, Hatigaon, Guwahati

THE HATIGAON MUSEUM BUILDING (AIM 4)

THE SOALU PLANT EXPLORED AT RAKSHASINI MOUNTAIN (AIM 1)

-X-

শিখনবাজৰ বাবে যোগ্য ঠিকাপাৰ
হে। বিবৃত্তিত আকৌ অভিযোগ কৰা মতে,

কেদ্রসমূহত সাত শতাধিক শৌচালয় আদি
টি আই কৰ্মী সন্থাৰ সম্পাদক গৰাকীয়ে।

কবিকৃষ্ণ জীৱন্ত মুগা সংগ্ৰহালয় পৰিদৰ্শন পৰ্যটন বিভাগৰ উপাধ্যক্ষৰ

বিশেষ বাৰ্তা, শুৱালকুছি, ৩০ ডিচেম্বৰঃ
অসম চৰকাৰৰ পৰ্যটন বিভাগৰ উপাধ্যক্ষ
নৱদীপ কলিতাই পৃথিবীৰ ভিতৰতেই
সৰ্বপ্ৰথম মুগা শিল্পৰ জীৱন্ত সংগ্ৰহালয়
'কবিকৃষ্ণ জীৱন্ত মুগা সংগ্ৰহালয়'
পৰিদৰ্শন কৰে। শেহতীয়াকৈ সংগ্ৰহালয়ত
উপস্থিত হৈ কবিকৃষ্ণ জীৱন্ত মুগা
সংগ্ৰহালয়ৰ শুৱালকুছিৰ মুগাশিল্প
পুনৰুদ্ধৰৰ লগতে কৰ্কট ৰোগীসকলৰ
পুনৰ সংস্থাপনৰ বাবে কৰা প্ৰকল্পসমূহ
দেখি তেওঁ আগ্ৰস্ত হয়। লগতে কবিকৃষ্ণৰ
ঘাৰা পুনৰ্জীৱিত হোৱা প্ৰাচীন বৈদিক
ছিন্ধু পথেৰেও পদযাত্ৰা কৰে। তেওঁ
শুৱালকুছিত উপস্থিত হৈ পদযাত্ৰাৰ পাতনি
মেলৈ ঐতিহাসিক আৰিমন্ত ৰজাৰ পুখুৰীৰ
পাৰত অৱস্থিত ঈশ্বৰ শ্ৰীশ্ৰী বড়দিঘি সত্ৰৰ
পৰিভ্ৰমণৰ পৰা ব্ৰহ্মপুত্ৰৰ পাৰৰ
প্ৰাচীন সাধনাৰ সচং কবিকৃষ্ণ শিললৈ।
তাত বিশাল ব্ৰহ্মপুত্ৰৰ মনোমোহা
পৰিৱেশৰ মাজত কিছু সময় কটাই

আগবাঢ়ে বাঘেশ্বৰী পাহাৰত সংলগ্ন
কবিকৃষ্ণৰ ঘাৰা পুনৰ্জীৱিত বৈদিক ঋষি
সুৱাদ মুনিৰ আশ্ৰমলৈ। আশ্ৰম পৰিদৰ্শন
কৰি বৈদিক ছিন্ধু পথেৰে সুৱাদ মুনি ক্ষেত্ৰ
হৈ প্ৰবেশ কৰে প্ৰাচীন মুগাশিল্পৰ কেন্দ্ৰস্থল
বৈদিক তঁতীপাৰাত। তাত তেওঁ তঁত
শিল্পীসকলৰ লগত মত বিনিময় কৰি
মুগাশিল্পৰ সাম্প্ৰতিক অৱস্থাৰ বুজ লয়।
ইয়াৰ পিছতে তেওঁ ঐতিহ্যমণ্ডিত শ্ৰীশ্ৰী
ঈশ্বৰ হাটীসত্ৰত সেৱা লৈ ডেকাসত্ৰীয়া
ৰাজীৱলোচন সন্ত বাপদেৱৰ লগত মত
বিনিময় কৰি উপস্থিত হয় কবিকৃষ্ণ দূৰ
চিকিৎসা সেৱা কেন্দ্ৰত। এই দূৰ চিকিৎসা
সেৱাৰ জৰিয়তে কৰ্কট ৰোগ বিশেষজ্ঞ
ডাঃ বিকুল দাসে কৰ্কট ৰোগীসকলক
বিনামূলীয়াকৈ যি চিকিৎসা সম্পৰ্কীয়
পৰামৰ্শ আৰু সহায়-সহযোগিতা আগবঢ়াই
আহিছে, সেই বিষয়ে অৱগত হৈ তেওঁ
ধন্য মানো। শেষত তেওঁ কবিকৃষ্ণ মুগা
সংগ্ৰহালয়ত উপস্থিত হৈ মুগাশিল্পৰ

প্ৰত্যেকটো পৰ্যায়ৰ পুংখানুপুংখৰূপে বুজ
লয়। তাত তেওঁ কৰ্কট ৰোগত আক্ৰান্ত
পৰিয়ালৰ সদস্যবৰ্গৰ দ্বাৰা মুগা বস্ত্ৰ
উৎপাদনৰ বিভিন্ন পৰ্যায়ত নিয়োজিত
হোৱা দেখি তেওঁ আগ্ৰস্ত হয়। কৰ্কট
ৰোগীসকলৰ পৰিয়ালবৰ্গক মুগাশিল্পৰ
জৰিয়তে কৰ্মসংস্থাপনৰ ব্যৱস্থা কৰি দিয়া
কবিকৃষ্ণ গৱেষণামূলক সংস্থাটোৰ যি সামাজিক
চিন্তা, এনে নিদৰ্শন আজিৰ সমাজত বিৰল
বুলি পৰ্যটন বিভাগৰ উপাধ্যক্ষৰাকীয়ে জনায়।
মুগাশিল্পৰ লগত সংগতি ৰাখি বৈদিক ছিন্ধু
পথেৰে শুৱালকুছিৰ সুৱাদ মুনিৰ আশ্ৰমৰ পৰা
তঁতীপাৰা হৈ কবিকৃষ্ণ জীৱন্ত মুগা
সংগ্ৰহালয়লৈ খোজ কাটি অঞ্চলটোৰ
গৌৰৱমণ্ডিত বুৰঞ্জীৰ সংবাদ লয়। বিশাল
ব্ৰহ্মপুত্ৰৰ ৰূপালী পানীৰ টো দেখি তেওঁ
শুৱালকুছিক পৰ্যটনৰ কেন্দ্ৰস্থল হিচাপে স্ৰীত
কৰাৰ মানস কৰে। উপাধ্যক্ষগৰাকীক সম্পূৰ্ণ
সহযোগ কৰে মুগা সংগ্ৰালয়ৰ শৈলেন চৌধুৰী
আৰু শৈলেন বৈশাই।

সম্পাদ
আগ্ৰস্ত
প্ৰয়াস
লগতে
মানব
কীৰ্তন
চলি
প্ৰস্তাৱ
হওক
গ্ৰহণ
সমিতি
সত্ৰ
নৱদীপ
এই
বট্ৰ
উপ
বট্ৰ
সম্প
নৱদী
সত্ৰ
বাজী
অৰা
কোষ
কাৰ্য
মুখা
কীৰ্ত
হ'ব

শিখনবাজ

টো
দান
হা
খায়
নী
বি
ক্ষ
গ
ম

জীৱন্ত মুগা সংগ্ৰহালয়েৰে 'কবিকৃষ্ণ'ৰ অনন্য প্ৰয়াস

শুৱালকুছিত বৈদিক তাঁতীপাৰা পথ মুকলি হেমভাইৰ

শুৱালকুছি, ১৪ ফেব্ৰুৱাৰী : অসম সাহিত্য সভাৰ পঞ্চদশতম শুৱালকুছি অধিবেশনৰ ঠিকলি-মুকলি পৰিবেশৰ মাজতেই সাহিত্য সভাৰ থাকিব পৰাই মুকলি হৈছিল শুৱালকুছিৰ ঐতিহাসিক বৈদিক তাঁতীপাৰা পথ। উল্লেখযোগ্য যে মুগা-তাঁতশিল্পৰ ইতিহাস অদৃশ্য হৈছে প্ৰায় ৪,০০০ বছৰ আগেয়ে সিদ্ধ সভ্যতাত, য'ত শুৱালকুছিৰ ৪,০০০ বছৰ পূৰণি মুগা সূতা পোৱা গৈছে। কিন্তু প্ৰাচীন কামৰূপ তথা এতিয়াৰ ■ ৯ পৃষ্ঠাত

শুৱালকুছিত বৈদিক তাঁতীপাৰা পথ মুকলি হেমভাইৰ

■ **সপ্তম পৃষ্ঠাৰ পৰা** উত্তৰ-পূৰ্বাঞ্চলৰ বাহিৰে বৰ্তমান পৃথিৱীৰ ক'তো মুগা উৎপন্ন নহয়। তেনেহ'লে সিদ্ধ সভ্যতাৰ নগৰবোৰলৈ কামৰূপৰ তাঁতীসকলে মুগা সূতা তথা বস্ত্ৰ পঠাইছিল নেকি? এই প্ৰশ্নৰ গৱেষণামূলক তথ্য অনুসৰি বিশিষ্ট চিকিৎসা বিজ্ঞানী ডাঃ বিকুল দাসৰ 'এজন বিজ্ঞানীৰ হিন্দুত্ব যাত্ৰা' গ্ৰন্থত প্ৰকাশ পোৱা শুৱালকুছি আৰু হাজো হ'ল প্ৰাচীন বৈদিক ছিঙ্ক ব'ৰ্ডৰ অন্যতম অংশ। এই ছিঙ্ক পথেৰেই এক জীৱন্ত উদাহৰণ তাঁতশিল্পৰে শুৱালকুছিৰ বৈদিক তাঁতীপাৰা পথ। প্ৰবাদ আছে যে ভগবান বৃদ্ধই মৃত্যুৰ আগদিনা শুৱালকুছিত মুগাবস্ত্ৰ পৰিধান কৰি পিচদিনা হাজোৰ হয়গ্ৰীৱ মাধৱ মন্দিৰৰ সমীপত মহাসমাধি লৈছিল। ঠিক তেনেদৰে বৈদিককালত শুৱালকুছিৰ মুগাবস্ত্ৰৰ সৈতে তিব্বতৰো আছে এক সুকীয়া সম্বন্ধ। সেয়ে মুগাশিল্পৰ সেই পূৰণি মৰ্যাদা তথা স্বাভিমান সজীৱভাৱে ওভতাই আনি মুগাবস্ত্ৰ সংৰক্ষণ তথা গৱেষণাৰ বাবে শুৱালকুছিৰ এক অন্যতম মুনাফাবিহীন বেচৰকাৰী অনুষ্ঠান কবিকৃষ্ণই অহৰহ প্ৰয়াস কৰি আহিছে। এই প্ৰয়াসৰেই এক ফচল 'কবিকৃষ্ণ জীৱন্ত মুগা সংগ্ৰহালয়'। তাঁতীপাৰাৰ সেই ঐতিহাসিক বৈদিক পথটোৱে দি যায় মুগাশিল্প পুনৰ উদ্ধাৰত এক অন্যতম মাত্ৰা। সেয়ে অসম সাহিত্য সভাৰ শুৱালকুছি অধিবেশনৰ লগত সংগতি ৰাখিয়েই বৈদিক ছিঙ্ক পথটো মানুষ্ঠানিকভাৱে যোৱা ৩ ফেব্ৰুৱাৰী, সোমবাৰে মুকলি কৰে প্ৰখ্যাত গীতাশাস্ত্ৰৰ বিশেষজ্ঞ পণ্ডিত হেম ভায়ে। পথটো মুকলি কৰি তেওঁ শুৱালকুছিৰ বিশিষ্ট চৰি প্ৰয়াত কৃষ্ণকাম দাসৰ কবিতা আৰু ধৰ্ম, পৰিবেশ সংৰক্ষণৰ লগত

সংগতি ৰাখি কিদৰে পৰিবেশ সংৰক্ষণৰ অৰ্থে গীতা, ভাগৱত তথা বেদৰ দৰ্শন ব্যৱহাৰ কৰি বৈদিক ইক'লজিৰ সোঁৱৰণত কবি কৃষ্ণকাম দাসে 'মই গছ' কবিতাটি ৰচনা কৰিছিল, সেই বিষয়ে আলোকপাত কৰে। লগতে বৰ্তমানৰ পাশ্চাত্য দেশত প্ৰচাৰ লাভ কৰা বৈদিক ইক'লজিৰ আঁত ধৰি তেওঁ কৃষ্ণকাম দাসৰ বহু বছৰ আগেয়ে তেওঁৰ বৈদিক ইক'লজিৰ গৱেষণা তথা ইয়াক কবিতাৰ মাধ্যমেৰে উপস্থাপন কৰা সন্দৰ্ভত মন্তব্য প্ৰদান কৰে। তেওঁ যুক্তবাস্তৱ 'ৱালডেন পণ্ড'ৰ লগত শুৱালকুছিৰ হাটীসত্ৰৰ সমীপৰ ৰাইজৰ পুখুৰীটোৰ লগত সুবাদ মূনিৰ আধ্যাত্মিক সম্পৰ্কৰ বিষয়ে মন্তব্য প্ৰদান কৰে আৰু চিকিৎসা বিজ্ঞানী ডাঃ বিকুল দাসৰ এই বিষয়ৰ প্ৰতি থকা ইচ্ছাতো সহানুভূতি প্ৰকাশ কৰে। ব্ৰহ্মপুত্ৰ নৈৰ ৰালিচৰৰ পৰা এই বৈদিক পথেৰে যাত্ৰা কৰিলে লগ পোৱা যায় তাঁতীপাৰাৰ শিপিনীসকলক আৰু তেওঁলোকৰ কথোপকথনৰ মাজেৰে অনুভৱ কৰা যায় শিপিনীৰ বৈজ্ঞানিক চিন্তা আৰু শিল্পীমন। এই পথেৰে গৈ ঈশ্বৰ শ্ৰীশ্ৰীহাটীসত্ৰৰ মাজেৰে গ'লেই পোৱা যায় কবিকৃষ্ণ জীৱন্ত মুগা সংগ্ৰহালয়। য'ত পৰিলক্ষিত হয় সময়ৰ আহ্বানত হেৰাই যোৱা পূৰণি শিপিনীসকলক পুনৰ উদ্ধাৰ আৰু কৰ্কট ৰোগী তথা তেওঁলোকৰ পৰিয়ালক এই মুগা প্ৰকল্পৰ লগত জড়িত কৰাই তেওঁলোকৰ আৰ্থিক, মানসিক, উৎকৰ্ষ সাধনেৰে খিলঞ্জীয়া জ্ঞানতন্ত্ৰ পুনৰ জীৱিতকৰণৰ অহৰহ চেষ্টা। কবিকৃষ্ণ দুবসংযোগ সেৱা কেন্দ্ৰই পৰিচালনা কৰা এই মুগা প্ৰকল্পই শুৱালকুছিৰ মুগাশিল্প পুনৰ উদ্ধাৰ তথা কৰ্কট ৰোগীসকলক উৎকৰ্ষ সাধনত অন্যতম গুৰুত্বপূৰ্ণ ভূমিকা পালন কৰিছে।

The Assam Tribune **READING**

Sunday

The connection between the famous 'silk route' of yonder years and the small town of Sualkuchi in Assam may have eroded over the centuries, but a renewed push is being made to re-work and re-vitalise the links. While traces of *muga* silk have been discovered during diggings at the site of the Sindh civilization, there are no known records of the silk being produced anywhere else, except in the Northeastern part of present-day India, specifically in Assam. The possibility of *muga* silk from Assam finding its way to the heart of the Sindh civilization, several thousands of miles away, many centuries ago, appears to be the explanation, especially since Assam was known to be part of the ancient silk road. This age-old connection had been explored and explained by physician-scientist Dr. Bikul Das in his book *Ejon Jigunir /Hinculna Yatra*, wherein he has concluded that Sualkuchi and Hajo in today's Kamrup (now) district of Assam were, indeed, part of the silk route or road of the bygone era.

Pushing forward the endeavour to re-link these small towns of the State with their glorious past, Dr. Das and the not-for-profit organisation founded by him, Kavirishna Lab, have been working to open a 'silk road' in the Tatpara area of Sualkuchi to give visitors a glimpse of the glorious past and the endearing present of *muga* silk, its growers and weavers of the area. The first 'walk' through this silk road in Tatpara was opened by prominent scholar Hem Bhui on February 3, during the Sualkuchi meet of the Assam Sahitya Sabha. The Gandhian leader praised the efforts of the Kavirishna Lab and its well-wishers for reviving this path, while also recollecting the pioneering efforts of Dr. Das's father, late Krishnaram Das, while promoting living in harmony with Nature. Hem Bhui went on to point out that late Das' poem, *Moi Goe (I am a tree)*, was based on the principle of 'Vedic ecology' long before the term even came into acceptance in the western world.

The walk through the new silk route of Tatpara leads through the bylanes of the area, along the houses

Vintage road revived

SUSHMITA GOSWAMI reports on a laudable effort to link the past to the present.

of the local residents as they are engaged in the silk producing and weaving activities. It gives an insight into the lives of the families of the silk worm growers and weavers of the area. Besides the walk, the Kavirishna Lab has also opened a Live *Muga* Museum at Tatpara, which showcases *muga* thread

produced by cancer survivors and their families. The Department of Knowledge Emergence and Social Medicine of Kavirishna Lab has been behind this museum. With Kavirishna Lab working on groundbreaking cancer stem cell research, led by Dr. Das himself, along with his associates, at his second labora-

tory at the USA, they are also in close contact with cancer survivors. As the Lab extends yeoman's service in most cases of cancer treatment in Tatpara and neighbouring areas – being a body registered at Tatpara, Dr. Das and his team at the Telemedicine unit of the Lab came up with the idea of interlinking a rehabilitation plan for cancer survivors and also to promote *muga* weavers. Under the 'Live *Muga* Museum' project, the Lab has been providing the raw materials for the spinning and weaving of *muga* yarn to cancer survivors registered with it. Once the yarn is ready, the Lab buys it from them and displays it at the Museum. It has been called a 'live' museum since the visitors get a chance to take a walk through the silk road and witness the process of silk-making themselves, making it a live experience for them.

The Lab has a long-term plan of sending out the *muga* span by the cancer survivors to the Buddhist monasteries of Tibet and other places, as there have been evidences of the use of *muga* silk in these monasteries several centuries ago. There are various legends of association between Buddhism and Tatpara and its neighbouring areas, particularly Hajo. Some believe that Lord Buddha had donned *muga* silk at Sualkuchi and attained Nirvana at nearby Hajo, the next day. While the belief may have no evidence to support it, the Kavirishna Lab is looking forward to re-introducing *muga* into the Buddhist monasteries very soon. The Kavirishna Lab is also developing a connection with the Viswanath Temple at Varanasi, which also has an old association with *muga*. They plan to reintroduce *muga* in Varanasi as a way of cultural exchange. A two-member team of Ph.D. students from the Lab – Lekhika Pathak and Seema Bhuyan had visited the Banaras Hindu University at Varanasi to deliver a talk at an international conference.

The novel concept of the silk road at Tatpara along with the 'Live *Muga* Museum' is sure to rekindle interest in the glorious past of the golden yarn of Assam, while also helping the present practitioners of the spinning and weaving arts eke out a better living.

(sushmita.assam@gmail.com)

কবিকৃষ্ণ যুগা বস্ত্রৰ দ্বাৰা আতিবেড়নীয়া বস্তিৰ পৰা

ছালৰ প্ৰতিৰক্ষাৰ গৰীক্ষণ

কবিকৃষ্ণ জীৱন্ত যুগা ম... লয়, শুবালকুছি
কবিকৃষ্ণ দূৰ চিকিৎসা, শুবালকুছি
... আহি. দি... হাটী

Jayanta B Sarma

13 March at 18:57 · 🌐

আমেৰিকাৰ প্ৰবাসী ডঃ বিকুল দাসৰ তত্বাবধানত আজি শূৱালকুছিত গঢ়ি উঠা কবি-কৃষ্ণ টেলিমেডিচিন চেণ্টাৰৰ কৰ্মী আৰু স্বৈচ্ছাসেৱীসকলৰ সৈতে আজি অসম স্বাস্থ্য সেৱা সমবায়ৰ আমি কেইজনমান উপস্থিত থাকি কেনেদৰে ৰোগীক সহায় কৰিব পাৰোঁ আলোচনা কৰোঁ। বিকুলে মুগা পলুৰ পৰা মুগা তৈয়াৰ কৰা মৰিব ধৰা শিল্পটো জীয়াই তুলিবলৈ চেষ্টা কৰিছে।

Abstract 3342: A novel indigenous knowledge system based approach to study cancer health disparities in rural population of North East India

Lekhika Pathak, Bidisha Pal, Tutumoni Baishya, Anupam Sarma, and Bikul Das

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Article

Info & Metrics

Proceedings: AACR Annual Meeting 2019; March 29-April 3, 2019; Atlanta, GA

Abstract

Background: India's North East is an economically deprived and politically unstable region inhabited by diverse groups of indigenous people. The incidence of cancer (mainly oral) is unusually high in the region. Through our KaviKrishna telemedicine care (www.kavikrishnalab.org) with collaboration of Thoreau Lab for Global Health (www.thoreaulab.org) we have initiated a longitudinal study in the greater Sualkuchi (50,000 population) area to identify different elements that underlie cancer health disparities. Specially, we wanted to develop an indigenous knowledge system (IKS) based approach (1) as an analytical tool to study cancer health disparities. IKS may be defined as a knowledge-emergence mechanism as a result of non-linear communication between an individual and his/her culture (1).

Methods: An IKS-based experimental approach was developed as follows. First, we identified 45 cancer patients (mostly oral cancer, age group- 30-65 years; 60% male) living in Sualkuchi. Second, we mapped out each patient's social network/support system through regular home visit, interviews, focused group discussion, and visits to attending doctors. Third, one group of patients (n= 30 out of 45 patients) and relatives were empowered with basic knowledge about their disease and the available treatments needs through regular focused group meetings. After three months, we repeated interviews/group discussion to find whether they communicated their knowledge/experience to generate an IKS-based system (1). The data were then fed into the IKS-network analysis tool, which we developed partly, based on hub-system (3) and thematic network based approach (3). 10 patients from urban area served as a control population.

Results: We found that 40 out of 45 patients find it extremely difficult to navigate the complex cancer care system due to lack of communication with treating oncologists/surgeons as compared to urban patients. 15 patients discontinued follow up visit mainly for this reason alone. 25 patients showed evidence of communicating through a pre-existing IKS-based system. Surprisingly, these 25 patients were positively responding to our care services/group discussion and becoming emotionally and psychologically strong towards managing their self-care.

Conclusion: Our study indicates that lack of communication is a major cause of cancer health disparity. An IKS based approach may enhance communication, and contribute to cancer care in rural India.

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